

Warrau

also known as “Warao”, “Ciawani”, “Guaraúnos”, “Tiuitiuas”, “Waraweete”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religion, South American Religions

The Warrau inhabit the Orinoco Delta of northeastern Venezuela and traditionally lived in villages known as Rancherías, which were comprised of about five to twenty families. This entry focuses on the time of about 1930. At this point, missionaries had established contact with the Warrau, but the indigenous belief system had not been Christianized. The religious and cultural traditions of the Warrau varied regionally as a result of extreme geographic isolation, but shared a common belief in the god Jebu, the presence of their sanctuary (house of the Jebu), priests (guisidatu), prayers and offerings to Jebu, as well as religious celebrations and dances (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:302). The belief system of the Warrau is not an official or organized religion, but an aspect of life interwoven with society. Further, the Warrau did not place a strong emphasis on a belief in the afterlife, and did not possess rites, ceremonies, religious scripture or credo (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:302). As such, the Warrau religion is most accurately considered to be coterminous with society itself. Presently, the Warrau fall under the jurisdiction of the Venezuelan administration (Dieter and Beierle, 2001).

Date Range: 1915 CE - 1945 CE

Region: Orinoco Delta

Region tags: South America, Amazon and Orinoco, Venezuela

This entry focuses on the Orinoco Delta of northeastern Venezuela ca. 1930.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ss18-006>

— Source 1 Description: Turrado Moreno, A., & Muirden, S. (1945). *Ethnography Of The Guarauno Indians*. Tercera Conferencia Interamericana De Agricultura, Cuadernos Verdes. Caracas: Lit. y Tip. Vargas.

— Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ss18-000>.

–Source 2 Description: Heinen, H. Dieter, and John Beierle. 2001. "Culture Summary: Warao." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

Notes: Source 1: Turrado lived and worked among the Warrau as a Franciscan missionary for twelve years. This account is considered to be a precise and detailed ethnographic account of the Warrau, and includes a review of previous records. Turrado's account was translated into English by Muirden.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Warrau have had contact with Christian missionaries. "After the agreement in 1922 between the Capuchin order and the Venezuelan government, Spanish missionaries arrived in the Orinoco Delta and in 1925 established the mission of Divina Pastora de Araguaimujo, the first organized effort to permanently penetrate the Warao heartland" (Heinen and Beierle, 2001).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Internal warfare was coded as absent or rare (SCCS variable 1649) , and the society is not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year period (SCCS variable 1654) (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: External warfare was coded as absent or rare (SCCS variable 1650) , and the society is not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year period (SCCS variable 1654) (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The religion of the Warrau is neither official nor organized; additionally, a lack of communication between regions produces a diversity of religious ideology and customs (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:140). "Holding political office was traditionally equivalent to the role of a major shaman, but since colonial times headmen and other officeholders have been appointed by outside authorities" (Dieter and Beierle, 2001). Now, political leadership has some overlap with religious leadership, but the political jurisdiction of the Warrau does not go beyond the local community (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). With a lack of an official, organized political and religious system, it cannot be said that the religion has official political support.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population,

numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 8500

Notes: "According to the statistics of 1941, they exceed 8,000; but they do not reach 10,000" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:9).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The güisidatu, priests of the 'jebu,' [god] official jefes [chiefs] of the cult, charged with praying, officially, and offering sacrifices to the god" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:310). Additionally, the regional chief, the gobenajoro, has the following religious duty: "From February to March each year he organizes or has organized the sacred dances jabisanuka and najanamu in honor and obeisance to the god Jebu, advising in advance by means of special commissions, all of the rancherías under his command so that they might attend the festivities and contribute, equally, some mapire of yuruma, güina of wild honey, and some canoa /canoe, trough/ of guarapo made of fermented sugar-cane" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:51). Witch doctors, known as "joarotu" are also present, and specialized in the sorcery associated with the treatment of various illnesses and ailments (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:166).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: The priests, witch doctors, and chiefs do not have supernatural powers, but are learned in the mysterious secrets of powerful sorcery (Turrado and Muirden, 1945, various pages including 51, 310, 165-168).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: "The Guarao [Warrau] do not possess a 'credo' or 'precepts' or 'rites' or 'ceremonies' or 'inspired books' or 'ritual books' (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:302).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 66, there are no large or impressive structures present among the Warrau (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 66, there are no large or impressive structures present among the Warrau (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "Sanctuary of the Jebu: dioso a janoko. – A little rancho [structure] made of temiche palms, three to four varas in length, higher than the other ranchos, constructed in the forest, behind the rancheria [village], hidden, very hidden from human sight, in such a way that it cannot be seen by any curious person, enclosed on all sides with walls and doors of temiche. Unlike other ranchos, entirely open, the sanctuary of the 'Jebu' is completely enclosed, in order to keep secret the sacred objects of the sanctuary" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:309).

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The ' mejokoji' –spirits, ' sitaba' – shades, souls of the dead, never die, but continue living" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:288).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Where do the souls of the Guarao...go when they die?" – And they [the informants] respond, without hesitation: – ' Kuay naria,' they go upward" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:287).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the souls of the dead] remain wandering through the world, near the places where they lived when they were joined with the body. They are transformed into sorcerer animals, trees, and birds, which the Guarao greatly fear" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:288).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the souls of the dead] remain wandering through the world, near the places where they lived when they were joined with the body. They are transformed into sorcerer animals, trees, and birds, which the Guarao greatly fear" (Turrado and Muriden, 1945:288).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the souls of the dead] are transformed into sorcerer animals, trees, and birds, which the Guarao greatly fear" (Turrado and Muriden, 1945:288).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "It can be deduced from this that the Guarao [Warrau] admit metempsychosis, the transmigration of souls. Many of their stories, myths, fables, legends, and traditions are nothing more than an endless recounting of transformations of men into animals, of the latter into birds, and the latter into men and animals" (Turrado and Muriden, 1945:288).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the souls of the dead] remain wandering through the world, near the places where they lived when they were joined with the body. They are transformed into sorcerer animals, trees, and birds, which the Guarao greatly fear" (Turrado and Muriden, 1945:288).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Interment is the typical form of burial. See questions below for details.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "After the sick person has expired, they do not wash the body or change the clothing. If he is wearing a guayuco [clothes?], he is buried in a guayuco, and if he died clothed, thus also do they inter him. They cover the body of the deceased with temiche palms and watch over it while they make the urn, the canoa, in which they are to bury him" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:280).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: The principal authority (Turrado) found no evidence for cannibalism among the Warrau (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:278-279).

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "In some of the rancherías [villages]... the Guarao [Warrau], after a certain period of interment, disinter their dead, gather up the skulls and bones, sometimes not completely stripped of the flesh; they wash them, put them in mapires, build a little rancho [structure] of temiche palms near or behind the ranchería, and there hang the remains and relics of the deceased from their family. If for any reason they change rancherías, they likewise transfer the bones and skulls of the dead" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:289).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: "In some of the rancherías [villages]... the Guarao [Warrau], after a certain period of interment, disinter their dead, gather up the skulls and bones, sometimes not completely stripped of the flesh; they wash them, put them in mapires, build a little rancho [structure] of temiche palms near or behind the ranchería, and there hang the remains and relics of the deceased from their family. If for any reason they change rancherías, they likewise transfer the bones and skulls of the dead" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:289).

– No

Notes: "After the sick person has expired, they do not wash the body or change the clothing. If he is wearing a guayuco [clothes?], he is buried in a guayuco, and if he died clothed, thus also do they inter him. They cover the body of the deceased with temiche palms and watch over it while they make the urn, the canoa, in which they are to bury him" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:280).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: "No prayers, promises, or sacrifices are offered for their dead" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:287).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "They put in the canoa [burial box] with the dead person all of the possessions which he had in life, clothing, necklaces, fishhooks, rope, arrows, harpoons, lances, maracas, etc., and what does not fit inside it they throw downstream..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:283).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "They put in the canoa [burial box] with the dead person all of the possessions which he had in life, clothing, necklaces, fishhooks, rope, arrows, harpoons, lances, maracas, etc., and what does not fit inside it they throw downstream..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:283).

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: All of the individual's items are buried with the individual, including any valuable items. "They put in the canoa [burial box] with the dead person all of the possessions which he had in

life, clothing, necklaces, fishhooks, rope, arrows, harpoons, lances, maracas, etc., and what does not fit inside it they throw downstream..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:283).

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: All of the individual's items (and wealth) are buried with the individual, including any valuable items. "They put in the canoa [burial box] with the dead person all of the possessions which he had in life, clothing, necklaces, fishhooks, rope, arrows, harpoons, lances, maracas, etc., and what does not fit inside it they throw downstream..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:283).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See Turrado and Muirden, 1945:280-287

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "When everything is ready, they load the canoa [burial box] in a curiara, if by necessity the route is by water, or four Indians carry it on their shoulders where there is a land route, and they go in a procession to the "joitanoko," to the cemetery, which may be far from, near, or even within the rancheria [village] itself" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:283).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, a high god is "present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). "They keep nothing in such secrecy, in such mystery, as the beliefs referring to the god 'Jebu,' [supreme high god] who he is, what he does, where he maintains his peaceful abode, what rewards he offers to his followers, what punishment he ordains for delinquents. The only ones who might tell us such intimacies are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death. This is why, when speaking of the 'Jebu,' the curious investigator is exposed to the telling of inaccuracies and errors, writing, even though involuntarily, the opposite of reality (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: See Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The god Jebu is "Living calmly in clouds of inaccessible light in the upper regions of the atmosphere..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The god Jebu is "Living calmly in clouds of inaccessible light in the upper regions of the atmosphere..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: See Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: "The god 'Jebu' is a superior spirit, never lovable and always fearsome, whom the Indians look upon with no love at all, but respect at a distance, because of the great fear in which they hold him" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The only ones who might tell us such intimacies [of the supreme high god] are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304). Although Jebu is capable of deliberate causal efficacy, "he lacks loving providence and does not concern himself with their happenings, progress, culture, and temporal and eternal well-being, nor does he offer them any rewards and punishments in the other life" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The only ones who might tell us such intimacies [of the supreme high god] are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Notes: "Despite being so remote and so near to the Indians, he lacks loving providence and does not concern himself with their happenings, progress, culture, and temporal and eternal well-being, nor does he offer them any rewards and punishments in the other life. Frowning and with angry eyes, always inclined to lower upon them the sword of punishment, he sends fevers, epidemics, and even death itself upon the timid, ignorant, and superstitious natives" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Despite being so remote and so near to the Indians, he lacks loving providence and does not concern himself with their happenings, progress, culture, and temporal and eternal well-being, nor does he offer them any rewards and punishments in the other life. Frowning and with angry eyes, always inclined to lower upon them the sword of punishment, he sends fevers, epidemics, and even death itself upon the timid, ignorant, and superstitious natives" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305).

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "...the 'Jebu,' that fearsome god of the Guaraúno [Warrau] who does not ask them for human sacrifices, fasting, and flagellation, as do other gods, but only for tobacco to smoke, water to drink and for bathing, and yuruma to eat" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304).

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: "In addition to this, the Guarao [Warrau] do admit to many, very many, an infinity of 'jebu,' whose seat, habitual dwelling, is in the sorcerer-trees, sorcerer-animals, and sorcerer-birds, in which habitually live the spirits, the souls, the shades of the dead, 'guaba-tuma a mejokoji,' 'guaba-tuma a sitaba,' which, in that state of transformation, of metempsychosis, are considered by the Indians as jebu, as inferior gods, as small gods" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:306).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Mejokoji. – These are the spirits, 'sitaba,' shades of the dead, whether Indians or Creoles. The Indians regard the 'mejokoji' always and everywhere as good spirits, who wander from one place to another through this world, dwelling in sorcerer-animals, sorcerer-trees, and sorcerer-birds, which are the habitual residence of one or many spirits, which, in this state of transformation, of metempsychosis, are regarded as 'jebu' or small gods" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:319).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "They can only see the 'mejokoji' during sleep, whether they sleep during the day or at night; but they do not always see them, only sometimes (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:319).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "In addition to the god 'Jebu,' in whom every good Guaraúno [Warrau] believes... the Guarao [Warrau] of the center of the delta of the Orinoco believe in the 'Musimu' and in the 'Masisikire Kuajebu'; those in the area of Pedernales, in the 'Borasire' and 'Mejokoji'; and those near Curiapo and Amacuro, in the 'Nabarao' and other spirits..." (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:314). See questions below for more details on non-human supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "This evil spirit [Masisikire] incites the Indians to sin" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:317).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: "The only ones who might tell us such intimacies [of the supreme high god] are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304). Although Jebu is capable of deliberate causal efficacy, "he lacks loving providence and does not concern himself with their happenings, progress, culture, and temporal and eternal well-being, nor does he offer them any rewards and punishments in the other life" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:305). Although Jebu can punish, it does not appear that supernatural beings are concerned with social norms and potential norm violations. The "religious concepts which they do have and preserve through tradition have no influence on the public and private morality of the individuals, families, rancherias [villages], places, and regions, inasmuch as the god 'Jebu' does not offer them any rewards or punishments in the other life beyond the grave, everything remaining in this world, everything ending with death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The principal ethnographer (Turrado, translated by Muirden) gives evidence for the superior high god punishing the Warrau, for example, causing illness. Other supernatural beings instill fear among the Warrau as "boogieman" figures. Not much is known regarding the punitive nature of these beings from the focal time period. See questions below for available detail.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "The only ones who might tell us such intimacies [of the supreme high god] are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "...there are no regards or punishments in the other life, which does not exist, but rather everything, everything, remains in this world" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:288).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304, see below for details

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "The only ones who might tell us such intimacies [of the supreme high god] are not the ordinary Indians, but the 'güisidatu,' [religious specialists] but they either do not know or do not wish to tell, because of the very great fear that the 'Jebu' might punish them by sending down upon them sickness, epidemics, and even death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:304).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not appear that the religious beliefs and practices of Warrau life are sources of morality. Rather, social, conventional, and moral norms seem to derive from the nonsecular elements of society. The "religious concepts which they do have and preserve through tradition have no influence on the public and private morality of the individuals, families, rancherias [villages], places, and regions, inasmuch as the god 'Jebu' does not offer them any rewards or punishments in the other life beyond the grave, everything remaining in this world, everything ending with death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not appear that the religious beliefs and practices of Warrau life are sources of morality. Rather, social, conventional, and moral norms seem to derive from the nonsecular elements of society. The "religious concepts which they do have and preserve through tradition have no influence on the public and private morality of the individuals, families, rancherias [villages], places, and regions, inasmuch as the god 'Jebu' does not offer them any rewards or punishments in the other life beyond

the grave, everything remaining in this world, everything ending with death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not appear that the religious beliefs and practices of Warrau life are sources of morality. Rather, social, conventional, and moral norms seem to derive from the nonsecular elements of society. The "religious concepts which they do have and preserve through tradition have no influence on the public and private morality of the individuals, families, rancherías [villages], places, and regions, inasmuch as the god 'Jebu' does not offer them any rewards or punishments in the other life beyond the grave, everything remaining in this world, everything ending with death" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "This is to say that the Guaraúno religious beliefs are not obligatory, since the 'Jebu' orders nothing for the Guaraúno and prohibits nothing for them. Therefore, to the good Guaraúno there are no truths for him to believe, or precepts to follow, or blessings to ask for, or rites or ceremonies, with which to honor the 'Jebu.' In a word, their entire religion obligates, is incumbent upon, the official class, the priests, piaches, or 'güisidatu,' not upon the private individuals" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Yes

Notes: "The official jefes, those who have the right and obligation to pray, sing, bellow, or mumble the 'joa,' prayers to the 'Jebu,' those who have the right to enter the sanctuary, to arrange it, fix it up, those who have the right to touch the sacred objects of the house of the 'Jebu,' the maracas of piachear, the 'Kareko,' the 'Jorujokosita' and the 'Daunona,' and, finally, those who have the right and obligation to offer to the 'Jebu' tobacco, water, incense, and yuruma, are not the private individuals, but solely and exclusively the güisidatu or priests, invested with the priestly insignia, that is to say, dressed only in a guayuco /loincloth/ and smoking an extremely long güina of tobacco and currucay resin" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: "In spite of the fact that the Guarao [Warrau] hold the 'Jebu' to be their god, private individuals do not maintain any relationship with him; they neither invoke him nor pray to him nor ask him for assistance for their needs, and, in spite of having a sanctuary in nearly all the rancherías [villages], no

private individual has either the obligation or the right to enter the house of the 'Jebu,' except for the annual religious fiestas in honor of the 'Jebu,' days on which the principal persons of the rancheria accompany the 'güisidatu' (chief) to the sanctuary of the god to seek out the yuruma and the güinas of honey deposited in the house of the 'Jebu' beforehand, offered and consecrated to the 'Jebu,' which they divide up and eat during the sacred dance of the 'najanamu' in honor of the 'Jebu'" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

— Yes

Notes: "The official jefes, those who have the right and obligation to pray, sing, bellow, or mumble the 'joa,' prayers to the 'Jebu,' those who have the right to enter the sanctuary, to arrange it, fix it up, those who have the right to touch the sacred objects of the house of the 'Jebu,' the maracas of piachear, the 'Kareko,' the 'Jorujokosita' and the 'Daunona,' and, finally, those who have the right and obligation to offer to the 'Jebu' tobacco, water, incense, and yuruma, are not the private individuals, but solely and exclusively the güisidatu or priests, invested with the priestly insignia, that is to say, dressed only in a guayuco /loincloth/ and smoking an extremely long güina of tobacco and currucay resin" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

— No

Notes: The Warrau have an annual religious celebration, consisting mainly of dances, which is held in the months of February, March, and April. However, participation is not mandatory for the average individual. (see Turrado and Muirden, 1945:302-303). "This is to say that the Guaraúno religious beliefs are not obligatory, since the 'Jebu' orders nothing for the Guaraúno and prohibits nothing for them. Therefore, to the good Guaraúno there are no truths for him to believe, or precepts to follow, or blessings to ask for, or rites or ceremonies, with which to honor the 'Jebu.' In a word, their entire religion obligates, is incumbent upon, the official class, the priests, piaches, or 'güisidatu,' not upon the private individuals" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

— Yes

Notes: The Warrau have an annual religious celebration, consisting mainly of dances, which is held in the months of February, March, and April. However, participation only mandatory for religious specialists. (see Turrado and Muirden, 1945:302-303). "This is to say that the Guaraúno religious beliefs are not obligatory, since the 'Jebu' orders nothing for the Guaraúno and prohibits nothing for them. Therefore, to the good Guaraúno there are no truths for him to believe, or precepts to follow, or blessings to ask for, or rites or ceremonies, with which to honor the 'Jebu.' In a word, their entire religion obligates, is incumbent upon, the official class, the priests, piaches, or 'güisidatu,' not upon the private individuals" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:303).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Warrau live in small groups called rancherías, which consist of about 5-20 families. Each ranchería is an independent unit belonging to one of several regions. Each region has three authorities, which are (in descending order of power) gobernado, kapitá, and fiskari. "gobenajoro. – The system of government of the Guaraúno [Warrau] tribes of the Delta of the Orinoco is to be considered and is in reality neither hereditary nor even elective, but patriarchal, purely patriarchal; being constituted by the major jefe, the supreme head of the tribe, the oldest father of a family, from whom are descended, directly or indirectly, all of the families which make up the ranchería; although there are exceptions, for example, in the ranchería of the Caño Guarina" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:49). Additionally, the Warrau have "no political authority [jurisdictional hierarchy] beyond the local community, e.g., autonomous bands and villages" (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In 1928 the Franciscan Capuchin missionaries founded a Centro Misional, with two boarding schools for natives of both sexes: the one for girls directed by the Capuchin Tertiary Sisters of the Holy Family; the one for boys cared for by the missionary fathers" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:128).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: "In 1928 the Franciscan Capuchin missionaries founded a Centro Misional, with two boarding schools for natives of both sexes: the one for girls directed by the Capuchin Tertiary Sisters of the Holy Family; the one for boys cared for by the missionary fathers" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:128).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that there is no food storage among the Warrau (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that there is no food storage among the Warrau (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "The river, ' naba,' is the railroad, the highway, and the side street to get from one place to another. To insist on making one's travels by land is entirely impossible, since there are no roads, footpaths, or any paths, because of the forest, moriche groves, mangroves, ponds and swamps, so natural in low and flooded lands" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:170).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: "The river, ' naba,' is the railroad, the highway, and the side street to get from one place to another. To insist on making one's travels by land is entirely impossible, since there are no roads, footpaths, or any paths, because of the forest, moriche groves, mangroves, ponds and swamps, so natural in low and flooded lands" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:170).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Because Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be the religious group. The Warrau police force (according to SCCS Variable 90) is institutionalized, and is assumed by the retainers of chiefs (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The national government took charge of the houses and haciendas, and the Gobernador of Tucupita ordered a corps of police to go there, having the intention of forming a pueblo which would bear the name of Avance /advance/, in place of the distinguished Centro Misional. Two years had not passed from the time that the missionaries left it when the police became sick; several of them died in Tucupita, having been brought from there. For which reason, when all was said and done, they ended up by abandoning it once and for all" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:128).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Because Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be the religious group. The "gobenajoro – The chief or patriarch of each region...judges and resolves the law cases of his subjects, in conjunction with the kapitá [captain] and the fisikari [financial officer]. He

determines the monikata, the penalties, for the guilty, thieves, adulterers, and miscreants" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:51).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Difficulties arising between some and other rancherías [villages] of different jurisdiction are resolved at the present time by the superiors of the mission centers of the Capuchin missionaries or by the authorities of the Territorio Delta Amacuro, in which the present-day Guaraúno [Warrau] of the mouths of the Orinoco live. Formerly, they were referred to the respective gobenajoro [chiefs] of the disputing regions; or, we might better say, to the oldest heads of families, the patriarchs of the disputing regions" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:52).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be the religious group. "The fisikari [financial officer], and in his absence the kapitá [captain], apply the monikata – the punishments, ordered by the Arima-güitu, gobenajoro [regional chiefs], to the guilty subjects" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:52). Although punishment exists, the extent to which this punishment is institutionalized remains unclear. With great variation between regions, punishment is not consistent among all villages of the Warrau.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Because Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be the religious group. The "gobenajoro – The chief or patriarch of each region...judges and resolves the law cases of his subjects, in conjunction with the kapitá [captain] and the fisikari [financial officer]. He determines the monikata, the penalties, for the guilty, thieves, adulterers, and miscreants" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:51). From this information, it can be assumed that a legal code is present among the Warrau. Because the Warrau did not have written language at the time this entry focuses on, it can also be assumed that law was verbally ordered.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "The present-day Guarao [Warrau] of the mouths of the Orinoco do not have any writing of their own, nor have they heard that their ancestors might have had it" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:195).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: "The Guarao [Warrau] indicate the years by stars and by winters /i.e., rainy seasons/, the months by moons, the weeks by Sundays, the days by suns and works, and the hours by measures of the sun" (Turrado and Muirden, 1945:200).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No evidence was found for the presence of a formal calendar (see Turrado and Muirden, 1945:200-205).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be coterminous with the religious group. The Warrau rely mainly on fishing, with hunting and gathering as additional sources of subsistence. More recently, small-scale agriculture has supplemented the Warrau diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Because the Warrau politics and religion are intertwined, the society is considered to be coterminous with the religious group. The Warrau rely mainly on fishing, with hunting and gathering as additional sources of subsistence. More recently, small-scale agriculture has supplemented the Warrau diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.